

Effects of Virtual Classroom on Performance in Essay Writing among Private Senior Secondary School Students in Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study titled: ‘Effects of Virtual Classroom on Performance in Essay Writing among Private Senior Secondary School Students in Abuja’, adopted a quasi-experimental research design. Four research objectives, questions and hypotheses were developed for the study. The population comprised of all the eleven thousand, four hundred and seventy-five (11,475) Private Senior Secondary School II students during the 2021/2022 academic session in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Fifty-five students were sampled for the study using the purposive intact class sampling technique. The study adopted test titled: Structured Expository Essay Writing Test (SEEWTE) for data collection. The instrument was piloted using split-half test method. The scores of the reliability test were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC), and reliability index of 0.90 was obtained. Simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that virtual classroom is significant on students’ performance in essay writing compared to those exposed to physical classroom. The study concluded that virtual classroom is effective in the teaching of essay writing. Based on this finding, the study recommended that school management should ensure that technological materials are adequately provided for the smooth and effective use of virtual classroom in teaching essay writing to students in private Senior Secondary Schools in Abuja and the country at large.

Keywords: Technology, Virtual Classroom, Physical Classroom, Essay Writing, Academic Performance, and Students

Introduction

The use of technologies in education has become a practice in many countries of the world. This innovation became known in many educational institutions around the world in the year 2020 when the outbreak of Covid-19 brought about a global shutdown in all sectors and activities that require physical interaction and contact. Thus, technology gained its relevance in education, especially in making teaching and learning stimulating, and taking over the stand of the traditional classroom approach (Matthew, 2022). Adding to the submission of Matthew, Godswill, et al. (2023) note that technology in education has the capacity to enrich teachers’ teaching style and approaches, hence, making teaching and learning effective. With educational technology, classes become more interesting, more immersive and fully interactive. Technologies offer the possibility of switching to a blended learning method, or a flipped classroom, which have been proven to be successful in learning all language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing). Moreover, they provide teachers with an infinite number of exercises and activities for different levels, which promote students’ active participation in the English language classrooms. Additionally, they enable teachers and learners to learn within and outside the physical classroom, keep students motivated, evaluating students with tests and exams, and other administrative tasks, as well as allow students to be much more creative, innovative, and participatory in the classroom (Carey, 2020).

Over the year, the teaching and learning of English language have undergone many changes. These changes have been attributed to the desire of language education researchers to make the teaching and learning of English language effective in learners’ development of language skills and their academic performance in them. At the start of the 16thc, the Grammar Translation Method dominated the language classroom. This approach aimed at developing grammatical rules and vocabulary in learners, as well as building the skill of reading and writing (Odumuh, 2020). While the above was advantageous in learners’ understanding of grammar, vocabulary and reading, studies from Mayiwa (2017), Nathan (2019) and Maisamari (2019) have shown the inability for the approach to develop the skills of writing in learners. Thus, learners produce written text that are extensive but meaningless; as there is no link between what teachers and learners teach and learn respectively, and the authentic world. Therefore, the effects of this form of meaningless text produced by learners have been seen on students’ performance in English language and essay writing in particular (Anderson, 2012). It becomes necessary thus, for language education

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researchers to search for a better language teaching approach that helps incorporate technological tools such as virtual classroom in teaching writing; in this case expository essay.

The communicative approach is a language teaching approaches that frames communication as the main goal of teaching and learning English language. This approach ensures that students can communicate effectively and confidently in real-life situations through student-to-student and student-to-teacher interaction via spoken, or written. Essentially, this approach aimed at making students to learn a new language by actually using the language to communicate with those around them. As an approach that promotes authentic use of language, the integration of reading, speaking, and writing are some of its core features, hence, making teaching and learning of English language interesting and purposeful. Another interesting aspect of this approach is the involvement of learners in groups; participating in the completion of authentic tasks and activities, aimed at meeting language needs and goals. Central to the above, is the use of language teaching materials and technology in teaching and learning writing (Godswill et al., 2023). Therefore, the researcher is motivated to incorporate the use of language materials, technology in particular to create authentic use of language in writing. Virtual classroom is one good example of the use of technology in teaching and learning writing (Yenus, 2017).

A virtual classroom is an online interactive platform or a teaching and learning environment where teachers and learners present learning materials and tasks with the aim of meeting educational goals. It is an online, live interactive classroom where activities such as teaching, learning, evaluation, presentation of materials, and grouping of learners take place. It is synchronous in nature; and allows students' active participation and promotes students-centered approach where learners can produce and present materials for class discussion and the general teaching and learning activities (Yenus, 2017). The use of Microsoft Teams, Google Classroom, Zoom, WhatsApp, Telegram, are some of the live, synchronous and interactive classroom platforms/channels that recent language experts propose for use in the teaching and learning of English language. Essay writing is an aspect of the English language where the skills needed to competently use the English language can be developed and enhanced in learners through virtual classroom.

Expository essay is one type of essay writing in English. It is the type of essay that requires a writer to logically present a subject or topic in a sequential manner. It involves the use of ideas in various paragraphs to develop a subject matter or topic. Thus, a good written essay requires the writer to develop a subject or topic to be discussed, contents to be developed, as well as supporting details that expand the ideas of the essay. According to Yenus (2017), the expository essay is popularly known as the process essay as it requires a careful presentation of a subject matter in a logical and sequential manner following an established pattern. Thus, he identifies the title, introduction, body and conclusion as the structure of an expository essay. Adding to the submission of Yenus, Godswill et. al (2023) identifies some vital ingredients of an expository essay. These include: content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy. In his postulation, the expository essay requires the writer to expose the readers to a good subject matter or topic using good and elevated language in an organized manner and paying close attention to grammatical components such as spellings, sentence structure, coherence and cohesion and punctuations. It is clear from the above that expository essay writing is that aspect of language skill that requires careful and effective teaching and learning. While many teachers may claim the use of best approaches and materials in teaching the expository essay writing, the researcher is motivated to find out if these approaches and materials are effective in the teaching and learning of the essay, considering poor performance of students in internal and external examinations where students are tested to write such essay.

For example, the researcher observes that students find it difficult to develop or create a suitable title of an expository essay. The effect of this is that appropriate subject contents that support the subject or title of the essay are difficult to develop by students. Again, the development of contents, main idea and supporting details at the paragraph level are other important skills learners find challenging in approaching an expository essay. The researcher in one of his assessment of students' external examination scripts observes that most students' essays lack subject content and main idea. The implication of this problem is that they find it difficult to organize details that support the ideas of a topic or subject. The researcher also notes that students find it difficult to write in simple, logical correct sentences, and appropriate use of words in context. These problems suggest that learners lack adequate skill for correct use of language in developing subject content in an expository essay. Another important area that motivates this study is learners' inability to organize the paragraph of their essays, and appropriate use of punctuations. Cohesion and coherence are two important aspects of an organized expository essay. However, the researcher observes that students' essays lack cohesion at the sentences level forming a paragraph, and coherence at the paragraph level forming the whole structure of a text or essay. Also, the researcher's interaction with other English language teachers in Secondary Schools across Nigeria has shown that students' lack the skills of English punctuations, especially in writing essay.

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Thus, students find it difficult to differentiate between colon (:) and semi-colon (;), they also misuse exclamation marks (!), hyphen (-), dash (–), full stop (.) and comma (,). Could it be that the materials and approaches use in teaching expository essay at the level of content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy are not appropriate and activity-based? While there is no empirical evidence to justify the above question, the researcher relies on the outcome of this study to justify the effect of using virtual classroom on students' performance in expository essay in private Senior Secondary School, Abuja. It has been established that communicative approach is an important aspect of virtual classroom; as the use of technology has been found to be an effective teaching and learning tool for promoting authentic use of language and making communication functional, purposeful and meaningful. Thus, Raymond (2017) identifies some authentic, simulative and interactive activities use in teaching expository essay writing, using virtual classroom.

The subject or title of an essay is the first part of the essay learners are exposed to. This is the area of in which the essay is set to address. It is the issue or topic the writer intends to write on. Teaching the subject or topic or title of an essay requires the understanding of different issues and areas of life. For example, the teacher may guide the learners to mention people, places, things and ideas they know. Doing this exposes the learners to various subjects and areas of life as well as their relevance to in human society. The teacher may also present a long list of events and ask students to choose the three that they have attended. They may also be guided to state three things that happen in each of the three events. Another way teacher could help learners understand the subject or topic of an essay is by guiding the learners to mention one discipline they would love to study. This will help the teacher guide the learners on how to structure the title or subject of an essay. Additionally, the teacher may also use pictures, images, or play recorded videos and audio on different careers for learners to make their choices. Thus, using virtual classroom will help the learners to understand and select their choice of career as well as have detail information about the content of the career. Also, teachers are flexible in the presentation of materials for the teaching of essay writing at this level (Moyo, 2022). Writing the introduction of an essay is another important aspect or skill to be developed in learners. This is one of the most important areas that the teacher is expected to develop in learners. The teacher is expected to provide appropriate activities for effective understanding of the introduction of an essay. The teacher may present five sentence hooks on different subject or topic and guide learners to identify the most appropriate for a given subject or topic of an essay. The teacher may present a short video on an interesting story and tasks student to produce one moral lesson, which is further turned to either a statement or a question, as sentence hook (Moyo, 2022).

Teaching the body of an essay requires the learners to understand the meaning of an outline and its uses in writing. It is the itemization of the main points or ideas to be discussed or explained in a text. It is a list of points or issues to be discussed about a subject or topic. In impacting this skill or knowledge via virtual classroom, the teacher may present an outline haphazardly and guide students to arrange them chronologically. This may be presented in text, pictures, motion images, video and audio materials. The implication of this activity is that it aimed at developing students' skill of content creation and development as well as elaboration of main points or ideas (Abiola, 2022). Other areas to be developed in learners include: grammar and language expression, punctuation marks and organization of the text. These areas can be developed through many class simulative activities, and group work. The teacher may present ten sentences on a given idea and guides learners to arrange them accordingly. He or she may also play a recorded video on a given topic and guide students to write a paragraph on the video. For punctuation marks, the teacher may present unpunctuated paragraph and guide students to punctuate it. For language expression, the teacher may present sentence stripes and guide learners to fix them in a given blank spaces of a paragraph. This will help develop in them the skill of language expression in essay writing using virtual classroom (Abiola, 2022).

This study is anchored on the Operant Conditioning Theory by B. F. Skinner. The theory is anchored on the principles of behavioural psychology especially with regard to how learning is achieved. The theory promotes reinforcement as a means of behaviour formation and modification. Essentially, behaviourists generally agree that learning is an enduring change in behaviour which results from the application of a stimulus to elicit a desired response. It is important to also clarify that an individual's behaviour is a result of learning. That is, when we internalize what we learn and are able to display it appropriately, that (skill, concept, idea, philosophy, etc.) which we have learnt become our behaviour (Raymond, 2017). Thus, the operant is said to be reinforced if the consequence increases the likelihood of the behaviour's occurrence. For example, a teacher may seek to reinforce learners' skill or demonstration of knowledge (behaviour) by offering a reward so as to reinforce those students' behaviour. A reinforce, therefore, is anything that strengthens the desired response. It could be verbal praise, a good grade, stickers, or a feeling of increased accomplishment or satisfaction. The theory also covers negative reinforcers — any stimulus that results in the increased frequency of a response when it is withdrawn (Raymond, 2017).

Relating this theory to the study, it helps the teacher to guide the learners in responding to essay writing, thereby producing what they have learnt. The outcome of the essay therefore determines the reward given to the learners by the teacher.

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If students' response to the essay is good, they get positive rewards like clap, treat, gift, marks, stickers, praise, etc. However, if their response to the essay is poor/bad, the learners attract negative reward. However, the theory aimed at retaining or sustaining good response to what is taught. Additionally, the theory is also useful in understanding the skills, strategies and channel (virtual classroom) to increase good academic performance as well as decrease poor academic performance in learners. It also dwells on teachers' approach in impacting knowledge in learners (Steven, 2020). For example, if a teacher wants to encourage students to answer essay writing questions in class the teacher praises the learners for every attempt (regardless of whether their answers are correct). Gradually the teacher will only praise the students that produce correct answers, and subsequently, only exceptional answers from learners will be praised and affirmed for continuation (Steven, 2020). Additionally, knowledge of success is also important as it motivates future learning. However, it is important to vary the type of reinforcement given so that the behavior is maintained. For example, the teaching and learning of essay writing is aimed at developing writing skills in learners for them to be able to understand the structure of an essay, identify a subject or topic of an essay, write a good introduction, body, and conclusion. Also, it is expected that learners understand and develop the skills of essay contents in line with the subject or topic, express their ideas in simple, clear and meaning coherent language, organize paragraphs in a sequential order, as well as use punctuations appropriately and other writing mechanics such as spellings, capital and small letters, and space (Raymond, 2017). Thus, this theory is relevant for the understanding of this study.

Many studies in language education have been carried out on the use of technologies in teaching various aspects of the English language and essay writing in particular. First, Davids (2013) conducted research on the influence of the use of ICT in teaching writing in some selected Junior Secondary Schools, Kaduna State. The study found that there is significant difference in the levels of appropriateness of the use of ICT in teaching writing and their experience and skills in ICT. The study recommended that ICT should be adequately deployed and used in teaching writing. Paulinus, Idongesit, and Nkasiobi (2016) carried out a study on the use of virtual learning on academic performance of JSS 1 student in English composition in Secondary School in Port Harcourt Local Government Area. The study revealed that there is significant difference in student's academic performance when virtual learning was used to teach English composition. Etukakpan, Maduka, and Christopher (2021) conducted a study on virtual classroom and academic performance of SSS II students in formal letter writing in Secondary Schools in Abak Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. The study showed that students exposed to virtual classroom performed better than those in conventional class in formal letter writing. Talal (2021) conducted a study on the effect of using Telegram application on improving writing skill for the students of English as a foreign language. The study discovered that there are statistically significant variations at the level of significance ($=0.05$) between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group in the writing ability of post-test due to the use of Telegram in favour of the experimental group. Also, Telegram application had a positive impact on the users, since it helped the students save and record their writing and other learning materials. Anabela, Debora, Deborah, and Susan (2022) carried out a study on the use of virtual classroom in teaching writing in Primary Education (grades 6) in Australia: A National Survey. The study revealed that teachers do not provide the appropriate teaching tasks for the teaching of writing. Also, the finding indicated lots of problems affecting the use of virtual classroom: poor network, inadequate computer materials like laptop, smart phones, tablet, etc. Eka (2023) conducted a study on the use of Microsoft Teams for teaching writing in Junior High School in Surabaya. The study revealed that teachers lack the skills needed for using Microsoft Teams in teaching writing. Godswill, Ngozi, Cajetan, and Ngozi (2023) conducted a study on enhancing ESL students' academic achievement in expository essay writing using Digital Graphic Organisers: A Mixed-methods Research. The study found a statistically significant difference between students' mean achievement scores before and after exposure to digital graphic organizer charts when writing expository essays. Despite the above areas revealed in those studies, there are gaps that the present study is set to fill. Thus, the use of virtual classroom (WhatsApp) as a channel through which expository essay writing is taught, and students' performance in the treatment of content, language expression, organization, and mechanical accuracy will be filled in the present study. Also, while the above studies used virtual classroom platform as such as Telegram, Microsoft Teams, Digital Graphic Organizer, etc., the present study used WhatsApp as the virtual classroom platform for the teaching of expository essay writing.

The clamour for the use of technology in every aspect of human society has demonstrated its relevance in meeting man's needs. The 2020 Covid-19 global pandemic that led to the shutdown of the world is a push factor that moved almost all sectors of the world to embrace technology for the conduct of formal and informal businesses, church services, and even education. This trend has since brought about change in the instructional methods and materials used in teaching and learning. To support the above, several scholars (Sylvester, Paulinus, & Udom, 2016; Anekwe, 2017; Mojtaba & Mahsa, 2018) consider the use of virtual classroom (an aspect of technology) as an effective instructional method of delivering lessons to students in today's world, as it helps stimulate learners and ease the teachers of the burden of teaching using the physical method. However,

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empirical justification is needed to support these assertions. Thus, the researcher is interested in finding out the effects virtual classroom have on students' performance on essay writing.

The researcher observes that the instructional method and materials used in teaching English language essay writing has not given much impact on students' knowledge of the English language essay and performance. This can be seen from students' performance in external and international examinations, where examination reports show that students' poor performance can be traced to the difficulty, they face in essay writing. For example, Godswill, Ngozi, Cajetan, and Ngozi (2023) note that students find it difficult to create and develop the title and content of an essay. Other areas include: language expression, organization and writing mechanics. These aspects of the essay writing are challenging for learners, as they lack the skills needed in writing a good essay. While the traditional teaching method has not been effective in the teaching and learning of the above areas in essay writing, the researcher is interested in finding out the effects virtual classroom will have if used in teaching students essay writing skills. Thus, the use of virtual classroom in teaching title of an essay writing, construction and development of good sentences that guide what the writer produces in each paragraph, organization of paragraphs in text, appropriate use of language and writing mechanics, are the main motivating factors that drive the conduct of this study, with the aim of finding out the effects of the use of virtual classroom in delivering these skills to learners in private Senior Secondary Schools, Abuja, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study

The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of virtual classroom on the performance in expository essay writing among in private Senior Secondary Schools students in Abuja, Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. find out the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of content using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom;
2. examine the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom;
3. evaluate the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom; and
4. examine mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Research Questions

1. What are the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of content using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?
2. Does any mean gain score exist in the performance of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?
3. Will there be any mean gain score in the performance of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?
4. What are mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of contents using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.
2. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.
3. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.
4. There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Methodology

The quasi-experimental research design was used in this study. The experimental group were taught expository essay using virtual classroom (WhatsApp), while the control group were taught using physical classroom. The population comprised of all the eleven thousand, four hundred and seventy-five (11,475) private Senior Secondary School II students during the academic session in the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. Two private Senior Secondary Schools were randomly sampled from

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the population, while the purposive intact class sampling technique was used to sample the students. The study adopted Structured Expository Essay Writing Test (SEEWT) as its instrument for data collection. The instrument was piloted using split-half test method. The scores of the reliability test were analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC), and the instrument has a reliability index of 0.98. The simple percentage, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and t-test to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Additionally, the instrument was administered to the students by two research assistants, who were trained to carry out the function.

Results

Research Question 1

What are the mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of content using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Table 1: Mean score of students taught expository essay in the treatment of content using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental Control	Virtual Classroom	26	6.21	2.32	16.88	2.64	10.77
	Physical Classroom	29	6.61	2.78	9.57	1.65	3.87
Mean Difference			0.50		6.41		6.71

Table 1 reveals the mean scores of both experimental and control groups which are insignificant. However, the post-test result showed that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 16.88 with standard deviation of 2.64, while the control group had a mean score of 9.57 with standard deviation of 1.65. The result also shows that the experimental group had a mean gain of 10.77 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 3.87. The table showed that experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.71 on the students' performance in the content of essay writing. Therefore, students in the experimental group have outperformed those students in the control group.

Research Question 2

Does any mean gain score exist in the performance of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Table 2: Mean score of students taught essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental Control	Virtual Classroom	26	5.93	2.03	17.58	3.69	11.66
	Physical Classroom	29	5.47	2.19	10.68	2.29	5.23
Mean Difference			0.49		6.93		6.45

Table 2 indicates the mean scores of both experimental and control groups. There is similar mean score for both groups in the pre-test, but for the post-test result, students in the experimental group had a mean score of 17.58 with standard deviation of 3.69, and the control group had a mean score of 10.68 with standard deviation of 2.29. The result also reveals that the experimental group had a mean gain of 11.66 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 5.23. The table therefore showed that the experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.45 on the students' performance in essay writing in the treatment of language expression. This showed that students in the experimental group have performed better than students in the control group in language expression of essay writing.

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Research Question 3

Will there be any mean gain score in the performance of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Table 3: The mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	5.58	2.82	17.22	2.45	10.68
	Physical Classroom	29	5.67	3.25	9.49	2.17	3.87
Mean Difference			0.09		7.72		7.79

Table 3 shows the mean scores of both experimental and control groups which are insignificant. However, the post-test result shows that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 17.22 with standard deviation of 2.45, while the control group had a posttest mean score of 9.49 with standard deviation of 2.17. The result also shows that the experimental group had a mean gain of 10.68 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 3.87. The table showed that experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 7.72 on the students' essay writing in the treatment of language expression. This showed that students in the experimental group performed better than students in the control group.

Research Question Four: What are mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom?

Table 4: The mean performance scores of students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom

Group	Method	N	Pre-test		Post-test		Mean Gain Score
			\bar{X}	SD	\bar{X}	SD	
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	5.94	2.04	18.59	3.69	11.65
	Physical Classroom	29	5.46	2.18	10.67	2.28	5.22
Mean Difference			0.48		6.92		6.44

Table 4 indicates the mean scores of both experimental and control groups. While there is similar mean score for both groups in the pre-test, the post-test result indicated that the students in the experimental group had a mean score of 17.59 with standard deviation of 3.69, and the control group had a mean score of 10.67 with standard deviation of 2.28. The result also indicates that the experimental group had a mean gain of 11.65 while those in the control group had a mean gain of 5.22. The table therefore showed that the experimental group had higher and increasing mean effect of 6.44 on the students' performance in expository essay in the treatment of mechanical accuracy. This indicated that students in the experimental group have performed better than students in the control group in mechanical accuracy of expository essay.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of contents using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Table 5: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	17.58	3.69	115	15.229	.000	Rejected
	Physical Classroom	29	10.68	2.29				

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Table 5 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught expository essay in the treatment of content using virtual classroom, and the control group taught without it, as $t = 15.229$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of contents using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom is rejected for the alternate.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Table 6: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	17.58	3.69	115	12.214	.000	Rejected
	Physical Classroom	29	10.68	2.29				

Table 6 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught essay writing in the treatment of language expression using virtual classroom and the control group taught without it as $t = 12.214$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant difference in essay writing performance scores between students taught language expression in essay writing using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom is rejected for the alternate.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Table 7: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	17.22	2.45	115	16.171	.000	Rejected
	Physical Classroom	29	9.49	2.17				

Table 7 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught essay writing in the treatment of organization using virtual classroom and the control group taught without it as $t = 16.171$, $df = 115$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in essay writing performance scores between students taught using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom in organization of essay writing was rejected for the alternate.

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in mean performance scores between students taught expository essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom.

Table 8: t-test analysis of mean score performance of Experimental and control group

Group	Method	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Decision
Experimental	Virtual Classroom	26	18.59	3.69	116	17.165	.000	Rejected
	Physical Classroom	29	10.69	2.28				

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Table 8 shows that there was a significant difference in mean score performance between the experimental group taught essay writing in the treatment of mechanical accuracy using virtual classroom and the control group taught without it as $t = 17.165$, $df = 116$, $P .000 < 0.05$. Thus, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in essay writing performance scores between students taught using virtual classroom and those taught using physical classroom in mechanical accuracy of essay writing was rejected for the alternate.

Discussion of Findings

Based on the analysis of the above data, the study found that virtual classroom is significant on students' performance in essay writing in the treatment of content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy in private Senior Secondary Schools, Abuja. This is justifiable based on the mean scores realized in the test administered to students taught content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy of essay writing. The study of Davids (2013), Paulinus, Idongesit, and Nkasiobi (2016), Etukakpan, Maduka, and Christopher (2021) and Talal (2021) whose studies on the use of virtual classroom on the teaching writing and students' performance also agree with the above finding. This therefore justifies that the use of virtual classroom in the teaching of essay writing and students' performance is significant. Additionally, the finding of this study also agrees with the findings of Anabela, Debora, Deborah, and Susan (2022), Eka (2023), and Godswill, Ngozi, Cajetan, and Ngozi (2023), as their findings also indicated significant effect of virtual classroom on students' performance in various aspects of writing in English language. Therefore, the use of virtual classroom should be promoted by concerned educational stakeholder for in the teaching of essay writing.

Conclusion

The importance of the use virtual classroom in teaching essay writing cannot be over emphasized as the findings of this study has justified its significant effect in teaching content, language expression, organization and mechanical accuracy as well as students' performance in the above areas. Based on this evidence as provided in the analysis of the study, the study therefore concludes that virtual classroom is effective in teaching essay writing and as its gives significant effect on students' academic performance.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Government and school management should ensure that adequate technological materials for the use of virtual classroom and competent teachers are provided for the effective teaching of the content of essay writing to students. Teachers should also be supervised on their use of virtual classroom in teaching the content of essay writing, and students' response to the teaching processes should be monitored for effectiveness.
2. The teaching of language expression of essay writing via virtual classroom should be stimulating, as to engaging all learners in participating in the teaching and learning processes for effectiveness.
3. Teachers should ensure that appropriate examples and learning materials are provided for the teaching and learning of organization of essay writing. Thus, emphasis should be place of the unity of paragraph (cohesion and coherence).
4. Finally on mechanical accuracy, the teaching of grammatical components, with emphasis on punctuation marks as well as their use in achieving a good written essay should be inculcated in learners via virtual classroom.

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